

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 128

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 128

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 128:0 A Song of Ascents.</p>	
<p>Psa. 128:1 "How blessed is everyone who fears the LORD, Who ^bwalks in His ways. ² When you shall ^aeat of the ^{1b}fruit of your hands, You will be happy and 'it will be well with you. ³ Your wife shall be like a ^afruitful vine ¹Within your house, Your children like ^bolive plants Around your table. ⁴ Behold, for thus shall the man be blessed Who fears the LORD.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 128:1 שִׁיר הַמַּעֲלֹת אֲשֶׁר־כָּל- יִרְאֵה יְהוָה תִּהְיֶה בְּדַרְכָּיו : ² יִגִּיעַ בְּפִיךָ כִּי תֹאכַל אֲשֶׁר־יָדְךָ וְטוֹב לָךְ : ³ אֲשֶׁתְּךָ אֶכְפֵּץ פְּרִיָּהּ בְּיַדְכֶתִי כִּי־תֵדַךְ בְּנֵיךָ כִּשְׁתֵּלִי זֵיתִים סָבִיב לְשֻׁלְחָנְךָ : ⁴ תִּנְנָה כִּי־בֵן יִבְרַךְ וְזָכָר יִרְאֵה יְהוָה : ⁵ יְבָרְכֶךָ יְהוָה מִצִּיּוֹן וְרָאָה בְּטוֹב יְרוּשָׁלַם כֹּל יְמֵי תַיִיךָ : ⁶ וְרָאָה בְנֵי־בָנִים לְבְנֵיךָ שְׁלוֹם עַל־יִשְׂרָאֵל :</p>
<p>Psa. 128:5 "The LORD bless you ^bfrom Zion, And may you see the prosperity of Jerusalem all the days of your life. ⁶ Indeed, may you see your ^achildren's children. ^bPeace be upon Israel!</p>	

References

Psalm 128:1

^aPs 112:1; 119:1

^bPs 119:3

Psalm 128:2

¹Lit *labor*

^aIs 3:10

^bPs 109:11; Hag 2:17

^cEccl 8:12; Eph 6:3

Psalm 128:3

¹Lit *In the innermost parts of*

^aEzek 19:10

^bPs 52:8; 144:12

Psalm 128:5

^aPs 134:3

^bPs 20:2; 135:21

Psalm 128:6

^aGen 48:11; 50:23; Job 42:16; Ps 103:17; Prov 17:6

^bPs 125:5

Targum

Psa. 128:1 A song that was uttered on the ascents of the abyss. How happy all who fear the LORD, who walk in his ways. ² [Happy] the work of your hands, for you will eat [it]; happy are you in this age and you shall have good in the age to come. ³ Your wife is like a vine that bore fruit on the side of your house; your sons are like olive plants around your table. ⁴ Behold, because of this, blessed is the man who is reverent in the presence of the LORD. ⁵ The LORD will bless you from Zion, and you will see the welfare of Jerusalem all the days of your life. ⁶ And you will see the sons of your sons. Peace be upon Israel.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is a continuation of the previous one. Therefore, the introduction and notes about a spiritual awareness of Psalm 127 applies to Psalm 128.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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